

COGNITIVE TASKS IN LOGICAL THINKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20830869>

Abstract. *This article examines the role of cognitive functions in logical thinking and their importance in the development of reasoning skills. Cognitive functions, such as attention, memory, perception, information processing, and problem-solving, play a fundamental role in enabling individuals to think logically and make sound judgments. The article explores how these cognitive processes contribute to the organization, analysis, and interpretation of information, allowing individuals to draw valid conclusions and solve complex problems effectively.*

Keywords: *logical reasoning, cognitive tasks, proposition, analysis.*

Logical reasoning is the process of using a rational and systematic sequence of steps to reach a conclusion about a given statement. Situations that require logical reasoning require structure, a relationship between given facts, and chains of logical reasoning. “Logical thinking begins with a proposition or statement. This statement can be either true or false. Logical thinking is a skill that, along with other cognitive abilities, is used in everyday situations. Logical thinking helps us make important decisions, solve problems, determine the truth, generate new ideas, and identify ways to achieve goals. Logical thinking is an important aspect of measuring a person's intelligence when taking an IQ test¹.

Over the centuries, many scholars have addressed logical thinking. In particular, Plato and Aristotle distinguished between the cognitive aspects of human nature (thinking, problem-solving, logic, etc.) and the negative aspects of human behavior (related to emotions, feelings, passions, and will)².

Later, Cicero introduced the concept of "intelligence" (from the Latin "intelligence", "ability to understand", coined by Cicero)³.

According to Miriam Webster (2006), the most common definition of reasoning is “the exercise of the power of judgment, imagination, or inference.” Charles Spearman argues that “if a person possesses any of the mental abilities that enable him to reason logically, solve problems, and generally excel in cognitive tasks, then a large set of tasks of varying difficulty can be designed to utilize these abilities.”⁴

Al-Farabi considered logic to be a means of drawing correct conclusions and systematizing knowledge, and argued that this process protects a person from erroneous beliefs⁵.

¹ Айзенк Г., Кэмин Л. Природа интеллекта - битва за разум. Как формируются умственные способности. – М.: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2002. – С. 28-29.

² Айзенк Г., Кэмин Л. Природа интеллекта - битва за разум. Как формируются умственные способности. – Москва: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2002. – С. 9.

³ Айзенк Г., Кэмин Л. Природа интеллекта - битва за разум. Как формируются умственные способности. – М.: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2002. – С.9.

⁴ Айзенк Г., Кэмин Л. Природа интеллекта - битва за разум. Как формируются умственные способности. – М.: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2002. – С. 12-13.

⁵ Фозил одамлар шахри. Абу Наср Фаробий / Таржимонлар А.Ирисов, М.Махмудов, У.Отажон. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2022. – 320б.

Iyun, 2026-yil

Speaking of logical thinking, we need to dwell on the views of the Jadids on logical thinking.

Saidrasul Saidazizov is an innovator-pedagogue, the author of the textbook "Ustodi Awwal", widely used in many schools. The author of the alphabet, taking into account the complexity of the Arabic script, as well as the fact that letters in the same line can have different forms at the beginning, in the middle and at the end of words, begins to teach with common letters that are written in the same way everywhere. This method has been of great importance in shaping reading and writing skills in young children. The sentences recommended for expressive reading in the alphabet textbook include stories written by the author, moral and scientific texts taken from folk oral creativity and classical Uzbek literature⁶.

Fitrat shares intellectual examples of logic and judgment in the chapter "Intellectual Education": "There are three conditions for making a judgment. The first is two correct judgments, the second is order, and the third is the transition from two known judgments to a third correct decision. The first condition is evidence, the second is the correctness of the thought, and the third is the decision."⁷. Fitrat also taught children that they should be told many stories and legends about great, intelligent, and strong-willed people⁸.

A. Avloni divided child education into the following four stages:

1. Educational education
2. Physical education
3. Intellectual education
4. Moral education

According to A. Avloni, developing the ability to think in children is a necessary and sacred task.

From the ideas of A. Avloni, we can determine that the famous innovator also had valuable ideas regarding preschool education, primary education, as well as logical and critical thinking⁹.

G. Asilova describes logical thinking as a psychophysiological process that develops through reading comprehension skills, and shows the connection between language and thinking¹⁰.

I.I. Lyubchenko, speaking about mental actions, characterized mental actions as actions depicted with objects and ideas and concepts about them. The scientist singled out mental operations, which are mechanisms of thinking in mental actions.

Comparison - with its help, similar and distinctive features and properties of objects are studied.

Analysis is the separation of objects of consciousness into mental parts, the identification of their parts, aspects, elements, signs and properties, and is necessary to understand the essence of the subject of analysis.

⁶ Fitrat A. Tanlangan asarlar. – Toshkent, "Ma'naviyat". 2009. – B. 269-283.

⁷ Fitrat A. Tanlangan asarlar. – Toshkent, "Ma'naviyat", 2009. – B. 285.

⁸ Fitrat A. Tanlangan asarlar. – Toshkent, "Ma'naviyat", 2009. – B. 300.

⁹ Avloniy A. She'rlar, pedagogik asarlar, drama, maqolalar va sayohatnoma. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2018. – 432 b.

¹⁰ Asilova, G. A. O'qib tushunish ko'nikmasi orqali mantiqiy fikrlashning psixofiziologik jarayon sifatida rivojlanishi [Development of logical thinking as a psychophysiological process through reading comprehension]. Ta'lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar, 2025.

Iyun, 2026-yil

Synthesis is the unification of individual parts, aspects, elements, signs and properties of objects into a single, qualitatively new whole, which, together with analysis, provides a complete and deep knowledge of reality.

Mental analysis turns into abstraction, that is, the mental separation of certain signs and properties of objects from their other signs and from the objects themselves to which they are inherent. Abstraction paves the way for deep generalization. The generalization operation is manifested in the mental grouping of objects and phenomena into groups that have the most important properties emphasized in the process of generalization. Generalization is the continuation and deepening of the synthesized activity of the brain with the help of words. It can be effective to present to primary school students logical thinking with the participation of logical exercises such as comparison, synthesis, analysis, classification and generalization, using examples of folk oral art, such as fairy tales, anecdotes, riddles and proverbs.

The subject of human thinking is cognitive tasks, which have a different content basis, which determines a different ratio of the subjective-actor, perceptual-figurative and conceptual components in their solution. Based on the above, three main types of thinking are distinguished: visual-productive, visual-figurative and conceptual.

Visual-productive thinking is characterized by the inclusion of direct problem-solving activity.

Visual-figurative thinking is a type of thinking in which the tasks in its content are figurative material, with the help of which a person analyzes, compares or generalizes important aspects of objects and phenomena. Abstract or verbal-logical thinking - is a verbal form of thinking that does not have a direct emotional basis, inherent in perception and imagery¹¹.

The development of logical thinking does not occur in isolation, but is formed and developed on the basis of visual-effective and visual-figurative thinking.

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